

BIOSENSORS: Introduction and its Applications

^[1]Kadam Srushtee V., ^[2]Paimode Sujata A.

^[1], ^[2] Shramshakti college of Food Technology, Maldad.

^[1]srushtee5@gmail.com, ^[2]sujatapaimode39049@gmail.com.

Abstract— Biosensor is one of the powerful and innovative technology used in the number of fields. It is a device which converts the biological response to the electrical signals. Various chemical substances are detected by using biosensors. It is used to monitor the presence of products, enzymes, by-products etc. It is effectively applicable in the field of agriculture as well as food science and technology and many other fields like food safety, defense, environmental monitoring, biomedical etc. Different types of biosensors are there for the target detection. Various types of biosensors being used such as enzyme-based biosensors, thermal biosensors, electro chemical biosensors and so on. Hence, specific biosensors are available to detect specific target substances. Maintaining quality of the food has become the major concern in food industry. The quality of food is mostly depending on microbial load. Hence, microbial biosensors are used in food industry to detect the presence of microorganisms and also different chemical compounds like methane and ammonia. Biosensors monitor the process of food products and maintain its quality throughout the process. In the field of agriculture, biosensors play a vital role by reducing the wastage of crops during harvesting and post harvesting. Pesticides also can be detected by using microbial biosensors have a wide scope in food packaging. The different sensors such as temperature sensors, leakage sensors are utilized during smart packaging which helps to maintain the food quality until it reaches to the consumer. It is utilized in smart packaging to keep the freshness and quality of food products. Nanosensors also have a huge scope in food packaging because it is helpful in determination of contaminants, microorganisms, and pollutants to achieve the freshness of the food products. Hence, biosensors have a wide scope in the field of agriculture as well as food safety and quality. Biosensor is an emerging technique in the field of food safety and standards.

Index Terms—Analyte, Amplifier, Bioreceptor, Biosensors, Transducer, Wireless sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

A biosensor is a device which responds to presence of a specific analyte (A chemical or biological substance that needs to be measured) by producing an electrical signals proportional to the concentration of analyte (Kulkarni & Joshi, 2014). Biosensor is the device which transfigures the biological response to the electrical one. Biosensors are useful in most of the fields we are aware of. It is majorly applicable in the fields like biomedical, agriculture, food safety and standards, food quality, environmental tracking etc. A major application of biosensor is in blood glucose sensing because of its abundant market potential (Kougianos, 2006). Biosensor is said to be an analytical device because the compounds to be detected are called as analytes. The analytes may include glucose, drug, pesticides etc. There is a transducer which is having a role to convert the signals for determination of particular substances. A bio-transducer is used for a biosensor system. Biosensor immobilizes the activity of enzymes and also the microbial load in the food which keeps the food fresh for long duration and also improves its quality.

II. PRINCIPLE OF BIOSENSORS

THERE ARE FOUR MAJOR PARTS INVOLVED IN THE WORKING OF BIOSENSORS NAMELY –

1. Analyte
2. Bioreceptor
3. Transducer
4. Signal amplifier

Analyte is the substance whose chemical composition is to be determined. Bioreceptor is a part sensitive to the substance

which is to be detected. Transducer is the part which transfigures the signals. The final part known as signal amplifier which amplifies the signal and exhibits the results which have been detected. The signals received may be electrical, thermal, optical etc. This reaction between the bioactive substance and the species (substrate) produces a product in the form of biological or chemical substance electrochemical, heat, sound, then a transducer such as an electrode electrochemical, semi-conductor, thermister, counter or sound detector changes the product of reaction in the usable data (Ruhai et al., 2013).

FIGURE 1: Structure Of Biosensor (Sassolas et al., 2012)

III. HISTORY OF BIOSENSORS

The history of biosensors started in 1962 with the development of enzyme electrodes by scientist Leland C. Clark (Kougianos, 2006). This biosensor was developed for oxygen determination and hence he known as a “Father of Biosensors”. The electrode he developed is named as “Clark electrode”. By using this invention, the glucose analyzer has been developed few years later. A number of studies have also been carried out to find a less invasive means to monitor blood glucose levels (Online, 2013). The development in non-invasive glucose monitoring has been reviewed in 2008 and it is expected to make greater progress in future (Online, 2013). Afterwards many other different biosensors came to rise including thermal biosensors, enzyme biosensors, and electrochemical biosensors. One of the advanced technique been developed is Nanosensors which can be utilized in all the fields we are aware of. Since then, research communities from various fields such as very large scale integration (VLSI), physics, chemistry and material science have come together to develop more sophisticated, reliable devices (Kougianos, 2006). Nowadays, in biosensors many of the advancements and new trends are on the rise.

IV. DIFFERENT TYPES OF BIOSENSORS

The biosensors are divided on the basis of biological materials using as follows-

1. Electrochemical biosensors
2. Glucose biosensors
3. DNA biosensor
4. Microbial biosensor
5. Optical biosensor
6. Enzymatic biosensors

• Electrochemical biosensor-

Electrochemical sensor is a device containing electrochemical transducers which is used to determine the composition of a system. In electrochemical sensing, the choice of working electrode material is fundamental to the success of electrochemical measurement (Viswanathan & Radecka, 2009). The principle of electrochemical biosensors is that the electro active analyte is oxidized or reduced on the working electrode surface, which is subjected to some predefined pattern of fixed or varying potential, and the variation on electron fluxes leads to the generation of an electrochemical signal, which is measured by electrochemical detector (Viswanathan & Radecka, 2009). These electrochemical sensors are in contact with the liquid electrolyte. It has a membrane through which gas can reach to the working electrode, then an electrochemical reaction occurs either it may be oxidation or reduction depending on the gas. Electrochemical biosensors are used to maintain quality of food because it is soundly used to detect the growth of microorganisms. Hence, it is also helpful for improving shelf life of product.

• Glucose biosensor-

Glucose biosensor is a device which is used to determine the level of glucose in people suffering from diabetes. It is helpful in reducing the side-effects such as heart failure, blindness etc. In clinical medicine, diabetes mellitus is the major cause of death in the world. This metabolic disorder

results from insulin deficiency and hyperglycemia is reflected by blood sugar concentrations higher than the normal range of about 3.9-6.2 (empty stomach) or 3.9-7.8 (2 h after food) mM(Online, 2013).

• DNA biosensors-

DNA biosensors are nucleic acid-based biosensors. These biosensors also have a huge role in food analysis. The DNA technique , including hybridization, amplification and recombination all are based on double helix structure of DNA(Iuni-iui et al., 1997). Nucleic acid hybridization is the underlying principle of DNA biosensors(Iuni-iui et al., 1997).DNA biosensors are surrounded by the sensitive part for proper sensing of DNA. It is smart and emerging technique in the field of food safety and standards. DNA can be immobilized on sensor surface with method similar to those used for enzyme based biosensors: adsorption, covalent immobilization, and avidin (or streptavidin)-biotin interactions (Sassolas et al., 2008). These immobilization technique also can be used to develop DNA microarrays (Sassolas et al., 2008).

• Microbial biosensors-

In food industry, it is an important thing to maintain the quality of food products from harvesting, manufacturing, packaging until it reaches to the customers. The quality of food is most directly dependent on the microbial load. Microbial sensors are used in food industry to maintain the quality of food by reducing the microbial load. This may lead to food borne diseases. There are also chances of contamination in the field of agriculture. Pathogens play a key role for contamination of crops. It may lead to wastage of crop during and post harvesting. Hence, its quality should be maintained throughout the process. Microbial biosensors are sensitive towards the pathogens and various types of microorganisms. It is an interesting topic for research to develop biosensors for monitoring food products. The main objective is to develop enhanced detection technologies with high level of reliability, sensitivity and selectivity with short assay time(Detection, 2013). These are critical factors for inspection of food products in industrial films considering the short shelf time of products and low infection dose for pathogens in food sample(Detection, 2013).

FIGURE 2 : Process steps in detecting pathogen in food sample (Lazcka et al., 2007).

• Optical biosensor-

Optical biosensor is one of the most common type of biosensors. It is based on the optical transducer system. Optical biosensor is basically used to produce signals which are equivalent to the substance to be measured. A number of optodes have been developed for monitoring dissolved and gaseous chemical and biochemical analytes in a variety of field of applications (Narayanawamy, 2006).

• Enzymatic biosensor-

Enzymatic biosensor is a type of biosensor in which the enzymes are used to produce the signal and determine the substance. Various methods for immobilizing of enzymes has been developed. Biosensors also used for immobilization of enzymes. Immobilization of enzymes is an important feature in designing the biorecognition part of enzyme based biosensors (Sassolas et al., 2012). There are various methods for entrapping the enzymes which are –

1. Entrapment
2. Adsorption
3. Covalence
4. Cross links
5. Affinity

FIGURE 3: Methods of immobilization of enzymes (Sassolas et al., 2012).

1. Entrapment-

Entrapment is the physical method of immobilizing enzymes. This method contains polymer matrix to entrap the enzymes. The matrix used may be of gel or microcapsule depending on the enzyme to be immobilized.

2. Adsorption-

This is also a physical method by which the enzymes are adsorbed by the vander waal forces in between enzyme and the surface.

3. Covalence-

In this method, the enzymes are entrapped or immobilized by covalent linkages or bonds. It is the expensive technique among all the techniques.

4. Cross link-

This type of immobilization is also done by covalent bonds . It forms cross links in between enzyme molecules and entrap them.

5. Affinity-

It is an advanced technique in immobilization of enzymes. In this method affinity bonds are formed to entrap the enzymes. It is new and smart trend in enzyme immobilization.

V. APPLICATIONS OF BIOSENSORS IN AGRICULTURE

Agriculture is nothing but the production of crops. It is important to maintain the quality of crops. During production of crops , various pesticides are being used to control various pests and disease causing microbes. Biosensors can also be used in agriculture field to maintain the quality of crops (Scognamiglio et al., n.d.). Various biosensors like microbial biosensors, electrochemical biosensor, optical biosensor etc are used to protect the crops. A biosensor has been developed for the detection of fungi causing damage to the crops. Nanosensor application in agriculture is a developed technique. Nanosensor is a device which is small in size but can sort out problems regarding wastage of crops in agriculture. They are used to detect the presence of pathogens, microorganisms, weeds, various gases etc. It keeps the food maintained throughout the process. Hence, the finished product of good quality can be reached to customers. Nanosensor detects the physical, chemical, physiological as well as biological signals. The wastage produced in agriculture during harvesting and post harvesting due to the improper practices. This wastage can be reduced by the use of nanosensors . Nanosensor is one of the emerging and new technologies to be used in the field of agriculture. This is also useful in detecting the environmental conditions. Environmental changes are an important factor which affects the quality of the crops. Biosensors detect the sudden changes in the environment and hence the possible loss of crops can be reduced in some extent. Nanosensors, nanomaterials, nanoparticles and many other emerging techniques has a huge scope in the field of agriculture.

VI. APPLICATIONS OF BIOSENSORS IN FOOD SECTOR

Keeping the quality of the food throughout its processing is the major concern before the food manufacturers. Various techniques are available to maintain the quality of food. Biosensor is one of the emerging technologies which are relatively used in agriculture as well as food sector. The applications of biosensors and also the nanosensors have a wide scope relatively in both the fields. The biosensors can be utilized from the raw materials to the finished products. The utilization of biosensors starts from production of crops. While cultivating crops, various pesticides and insecticides are spread to control the growth of pests, insects and other microorganisms. Most commonly a fungus grow on the crops and causes the wastage. To reduce this wastage, microbial biosensors are used. The biosensors are used in the food-agro supply chain for maintaining the quality and safety throughout the process. While processing of food products, there are more chances of contamination. Nanosensors are used to reduce the contamination. The different sensors are provided to detect the components which may lead to wastage of the product. Temperature sensors , leakage sensors, oxygen indicators, sensors that indicates smell and

taste are used to detect the problems in processing. These sensors monitors the process of food manufacturing and immediately provides signals if any problem occurs. The nutritional components of food products such as carbohydrates, amino acids, vitamins etc can also be determined by biosensors. Freshness of food is monitored by time and temperature sensors and oxygen sensors throughout the process. By the use of biosensors the quality of food is maintained throughout the processing until it reaches to the customers. Biosensors are capable to hold a promise of revolutionizing many aspects of food and dairy industry and satisfies the most essential needs of measurement of on-line food quality attributes (Kulkarni & Joshi, 2014).

FIGURE 4: Food-Agri supply chain (Researchgate.net).

VII. BIOSENSORS IN FOOD PACKAGING

Food packaging is the process of enclosing the food to protect it from physical, chemical and environmental factors. Protection is one of the major function of food packaging. Biosensors are effectively used in the smart packaging. The quality of food is usually determined by the environments in which the products are packaged and delivered to the customers, during which time any number of events can occur to negatively impact the quality of the products (Park et al., 2015). Smart packaging is the intelligent packaging in which in-built sensors are used to monitor the food products. It is a new and convenient technique to monitor the freshness of food products. Different food packaging materials with indicators or sensors are available in the market, including time-temperature integrators (TTI), freshness indicators etc (Park et al., 2015). Sensors change the signals according to the changes in environmental conditions. Cost effectiveness is always an important factor, it is especially important for

sensors/indicators that will be integrated into the packaging material (Park et al., 2015). Biosensor help to correct disadvantages of packaging and has a wide scope in the sector of food packaging.

VIII. APPLICATIONS OF BIOSENSORS IN ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING

Environmental condition plays an important role in better yield of crops. The pollutants, sudden environmental changes can affect yield and quality of crops. Hence, it is an essential thing to monitor the environmental changes. The environmental pollutants may cause toxicity to the crops. This may lead to food-borne diseases. Biosensors help to determine the changes happening in the environment throughout the process of cultivation until the harvesting. It plays a major role in maintaining quality of crops and reduces the wastage of crops or raw material which is to be provided in a food sector for further processing. Hence, biosensors are helpful in Agri-food supply chain as it maintains the quality of raw material until it reaches for processing. During processing of raw materials, other different kinds of biosensors are utilized and quality assured food products are prepared.

IX. FUTURE PROSPECTS IN BIOSENSORS

Biosensors can be utilized in all the fields we are aware of. Biosensors have a major role in the agriculture as well as food sector. Nowadays, biosensors have become a topic of interest to the researchers due to its cost effectiveness as well as its accuracy. There are various sensors available in market such as electrochemical biosensors, optical biosensors, glucose biosensors etc. The most emerging technique in the biosensors is **wireless sensors**. In recent years, research into optical platforms for SPR biosensors has been increasingly application-oriented, targeting specific applications areas and providing solution meeting unique requirements of specific applications (Chem, 2003). A wireless sensor network is a system comprised of radio frequency (RF) transceivers, sensors, microcontrollers and power source (Wang et al., 2006). It is a technology which is under the development stage (Sassolas et al., 2008).

• Why wireless sensors-

An obvious advantage of wireless transmission is a significant reduction and simplification in wiring and harness (Wang et al., 2006). Wireless sensors allow otherwise impossible sensor applications, such as monitoring dangerous, hazardous, unwired or remote areas or locations (Wang et al., 2006).

• Hardware and software required in wireless sensors-

Hardware required for wireless sensors are (1) robust radio technology, (2) low cost, energy efficient processor, (3) Flexible I/O for various sensors, (4) long lifetime energy source, (5) flexible open source development platform (Wang et al., 2006). Software requirements for wire sensors are (1) small footprint to run on small processors, (2) efficient energy use, (3) capability of fine grained concurrency, (4)

high modularity, (5) robust and hoc mesh networking of low power (Wang et al., 2006).

X. CONCLUSION

Biosensor is the technique applicable for the entire field. Biosensors have a huge market for food analysis. The utilization of biosensors starts from cultivation of crop until it reaches to the customers. Biosensors plays a vital role in providing safe and quality food. It is a cost effective technique, easy to use and has an accurate results. It is an innovative technique can be used in low cost. Nowadays, the research on emerging nanotechnology in the biosensors is under the focus of researchers. Biosensor is a technique which can be utilized in the food industry to provide safe and quality food to the customers in low cost. A wireless sensor is a new and developing trend in biosensors. Biosensors gives the direct senses regarding the problems may occur during manufacturing of food products. It also reduces the wastage of crops in agriculture field which is ultimately helpful in maintaining quality of finished products. The utilization of biosensors in food sector improves the taste, color, flavor and many other quality parameters. It is also helpful in extending the shelf life of food products. As the development in biosensors continues to emerge, its applicability in food industry will increase potentially. Biosensors also have a major role in fields like biomedical, environmental science and many more. Hence, biosensor is a new and smart trend applicable in the entire fields.

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